

Ottawa Transitway Rock Slope Risk Assessment

João Renato R. Prandina

Dept. of Civil Engineering, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, ON, Canada

Gongda Lu

Dept. of Civil Engineering, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, ON, Canada

ABSTRACT

Ottawa's Transitway has been the core infrastructure of an efficient and great BRT system of Canada, exclusive roads with steep rock slopes along more than 3,2 km which are most of the time exposed, showing pieces of evidence that the risk for the users may have been increasing. In fact, the low number of geological events and its neglected consequences related to the rock slopes until now have created a perception of a low-risk area for all the local society. The main objective of this work is the assessment of the risk inherent to the conditions posed by these rock slopes using the geotechnical engineering point of view. The limestone of the Transitway is deteriorating and this is a notable aspect for the geotechnical considerations. A practical method for rockfall, the RHRS – Rockfall Hazard Rating System was chosen. The results show hazards rating far from negligible. And because Ottawa is inside a very active earthquake zone, the hazards of earthquake related to a more important failure, the planar one, is studied. The pseudo-static approach performed showed that a failure is not impossible at all. Once the hazard of rockfall and rockslide are relevant, the vulnerability of the elements subjected to an eventual landslide and its amounts are presented. An evaluation of the risk is conducted, showing the minimum reasonable direct consequences for some scenarios that may be caused by rockfall and a rockslide. As conclusions, the risk assessment confirmed its relevance, earthquakes may cause landslides even though geological conditions are not the worst and the hazards are not the greatest. Factor of Safety has to be precisely updated to validate the risk status of the area.

RÉSUMÉ

Le Transitway d'Ottawa a été la principale infrastructure d'un système BRT efficace et extraordinaire du Canada, routes exclusives avec des pentes rocailleuses abruptes sur plus de 3,2km qui sont le plus souvent exposés, montrant des preuves que le risque pour les usagers a augmenté. En fait, la faible occurrence d'événements géologiques et ses conséquences négligées liées aux pentes de roches ont créé jusqu'à présent la perception d'une zone à faible risque. L'objectif principal de ce travail est l'évaluation du risque dû aux conditions imposées par ces pentes de roches en utilisant le point de vue de l'ingénierie géotechnique. Le calcaire du Transitway se détériore et il s'agit d'un aspect remarquable pour les considérations géotechniques. Une méthode pratique pour la chute des pierres, le RHRS – Rockfall Hazard Rating System, a été choisie pour la présente étude. Les résultats montrent que les dangers sont loin d'être négligeables. Étant donné qu'Ottawa se situe dans une zone sismique très active, les dangers liés à un effondrement plus important, le planar, sont étudiés. L'approche pseudo-statistique réalisée a démontré que l'effondrement n'est pas du tout impossible. Une fois que le danger de chute de pierre et de glissement de pierre devient important, la vulnérabilité des éléments assujettis à un ultime glissement de terrain et de ses composés est présentée. Une évaluation du risque est menée, démontrant les conséquences minimales raisonnables directes pour quelques scénarios qui peuvent être causés par la chute de pierres ou par le glissement de pierres. En guise de conclusion, l'évaluation de risque confirme sa pertinence, les tremblements de terre peuvent causer des glissements de terrain même si les conditions ne sont pas les pires et les dangers ne sont pas les plus grands. Le facteur de sécurité doit être précisément mis à jour pour valider le statut de risque de l'aire.

1 INTRODUCTION

The infrastructure is a pre-investment upon which the economic engine runs and quality of life is assured. Ottawa's Transitway roads are a public infrastructure to support the safety, security, mobility, well-being and prosperity of Canadians. However, the roads in many cities of Canada which are in poor conditions need CAD\$ 91 billion in investments to recover the minimum safety and quality (Canadian Infrastructure Report, 2012).

Transitway corridors run beside several rock slopes, with 30 km of exclusive road corridors (Van Wilkins, 2004). They are the essential infrastructure for the public transportation system in Ottawa, Ontario, which operates one of the largest BRT systems in North America. It carries over 200,000 daily riders on the Ottawa Transitway, achieving peak capacities of 10,000 passengers per hour per direction. The final

number in the year of 2011 was 103.5 million of individual trips (OC Transpo, 2012).

Rock slopes and risk analysis are an important subject for existing infrastructures. Therefore, this work goes beyond the qualitative concepts and assesses the hazard, stability, and risk posed to commuters and, so, to the City.

1.1 Focusing in Transitway and Rock Slopes Risks

Between Dominion Station and Bayview Station, there are several different heights, geometries and geotechnical configuration of steep rock slopes. The rock shows off forming the slopes in the face front. On the top of the geology profile, a thin soil layer covers the landscape (Fig. 1). Different heights of unstable rock slopes and this layers of soil are stabilized by retaining walls in some stretches, which are typical elements of the cross section of the Transitway.

Figure 1. Typical view of Transitway cross section (from Mercier, 2008)

As a natural law, a slope deteriorates. Pieces of evidence of this deterioration can be seen in the field: many types of geological and geotechnical manifestations are externalized as result of the aging effect, weathering. Additionally, slope angle and presence of water widen the challenge of a rock slope. Fig. 2 presents an overall view of the Factor of Safety related to the angle of the slope.

Figure 2. Factor of safety range considering the slope inclination (FHWA, 1989).

2 GEOLOGICAL HAZARDS IN TRANSITWAY

The worst event from the behavior of a slope is the failure, considered a hazard against human society. A failure occurs when a large or a small amount of mass of rock or soil flicks to the lowest level of the slopes. Additionally, a slope can lead a system of roads and its vicinity to other types of geological hazards such as flooding, block falls, partial rupture or even landslides.

Once a failure in the rock or soil slopes of Transitway happens, it is supposed to affect in some intensity the traffic flow of the buses or the train system, the public utilities, and properties surrounding the area of instability. In the worst scenario for life, a speeding bus or train can be caught or hit a mass of rock or soil displaced by the failure.

This risk assessment should point the instability issues, the hazards, the vulnerability of the Transitway and cost estimation of the amounts related to these hazards. These risks are inherent in any public transportation system, and in

the case of some inconvenient event such as rockslides, the knowledge imposed to the predictions and assessment will allow faster resuming of the operations.

2.1 Evidences of Rock Slope Instability

The rock slopes of Transitway are mostly exposed. It is easy to verify the evidence of the geotechnical hazards which are currently occurring: it has been observed small amounts of debris along Transitway.

A slope pulls a reasonable number of geological hazards specifically related to its geometric configuration. The inclined surface of a slope, with bigger or a smaller angle, invites water to participate in the system. Water is a factor of instability, and in an area with weather below zero Celsius for many months, it induces another range of processes for a rock slope massif that also contributes to its instabilization.

It is important to state that the stability of a slope changes with time. Hencher (2012) presented the concept of changes in slope stability with time: each age, one different Factor of Safety. Therefore, risk assessment of the hazards of a rock slope necessarily has to include the current and updated geological conditions.

3 GEOLOGY OF OTTAWA'S TRANSITWAY

In a slope, one can see the rock type, soil cover/thickness of other layers, directly on its surface which turns to be an initial overview of the geology. Therefore, this initial observation allows to performing the superficial assessment of the site characteristics.

The stretch of the Transitway considered in this work is inside a "rock channel." Precisely, it is the sedimentary rock limestone, with its well-studied first set of joint established due to the embedment formation.

Usually, the discontinuities will govern the failure mode, which forms the basis for the study of the stability of the rock slope. An accurate rock slope stability analysis needs a good geological survey to determine all the discontinuities to enable the choice for the correct approach and method to analyze its stability.

Hencher (2012) presents an overall scope of a site investigation to be considered to establish a geomechanical model for the behavior analysis, and also a hazard prediction of the rock slope:

- 1) Hazards constraints during construction and in the long term;
- 2) Assess and record the site characteristics;
- 3) Geological profile at site;
- 4) Physical properties of soil and rock units and design parameters;
- 5) Changes with time.

The geological status is a primary source of information. The rock slopes are deteriorating because it is showing new volumes of debris and cracks on its exposed surface each week. Additionally, there are very constant vibrations coming from the shock waves generated by the buses that pass very close to the rock slopes. There is also the constant presence of water due to the geometry which may accelerate the deterioration. There are several image registers of rockfall, especially small blocks up to 200 mm. They were recorded

between the dates of October 5th until November 26th in many images obtained in different dates.

4 ROCK MASSIFS HAZARDS

The stretch of the Transitway considered in this work is inside an excavated rock. It is a man-made infrastructure, and the slopes one of the consequences of the design.

The rockfall itself is a type of failure of a rock slope. But the amount of mass can cause different and smaller problems than a large scale failure. Therefore, this work suggests two failure modes to be studied: rockfall and rockslide.

4.1 Rockfall in Transitway

This instability issue is harmful to users than it is for the slope itself. The deterioration, the infiltration of water and vibration of vehicles may have induced more cracks to the rock slopes. A useful tool to accomplish an initial assessment and analyze the rockfall in Transitway is the RHRS – Rockfall Hazard Rating System, widely known to evaluate the hazard of rockfall.

This phenomenon can be seen in the face of the slopes, and the consequences for the slope are the increasing of the deterioration and debris in the virtual ditch, a plane side walk. As a first tool, Pantelidis (2009) also stated the same. FHWA (1993) detailed the RHRS, and this assessment follows its guidelines. The literature is full of examples, and so the decision to use it seems appropriate for an initial assessment of the type of hazards: rockfall.

The categories in RHRS are slope height (1); ditch effectiveness (2); average vehicle risk (AVR,3); percent of decision site distance (4); roadway width including paved shoulders (5). Also, five geologic characteristics of the slope, two regarding discontinuities: structural condition (6); rock friction (7); and two items regarding erosion: structural condition (8); differences in erosion rates (9); block size (10). And the last two: climate and presence of water on the slope (11); rockfall history (12).

The geometric category starts with the total height of the slope. Heights are divided in 25, 50, 75 and 100 feet, which would receive 3, 9, 27 and 81 score points considering the case.

Figure 3. Cross section of the Transitway (Mercier, 2008)

For the Transitway, AVR is a constant and growing value along one week day and is certainly lower on the weekends. Besides, there are differences in rates at daylight traffic hours and overnight hours. The total number of vehicles was estimated from OC Transpo (2012) report, and that Transitway is responsible for 63% of trips (Mercier, 2008).

Performing an analysis in Ottawa Transitway rock slopes with RHRS leads to the results showed in Table 1 for different slope height from 5 to 10 m. In this study, the heights of the slopes were changed and also the length with other parameters fixed. For the slopes near Westboro and Tunney's Pasture Stations, the lengths of 150 and 250 m were adopted according to great sectors of exposed rock slopes.

The results of RHRS analysis showed a small to intermediary hazard rating for rockfall. The slopes 1 to 6 showed RHRS score between 210 and 288, which are between the lower and the intermediary level of the RHRS exponential scale.

These results were normalized by the maximum score, 972 and it can be seen the range for the slopes is from 0.22 to 0.30. This scale of RHRS is exponential.

Despite the small to intermediary level of rockfall hazards, the suggestions for an appropriate ditch width for these rock slopes made by Peckover and Kerr (1977) are between 4.0 and 4.5 m.

In addition, their criteria present a minimum depth between 1.0 and 1.2 m.

Therefore, even though the hazards of the rock slopes are between low and intermediary, the appropriate width and depth of a ditch for Transitway is 4 m. And the current Transitway ditch does not match the cited design criteria: its available space for a ditch is 2.5 m, and the depth is zero.

The existence of rockfall hazard is a current reality for the area and once the ditch is lower than preconized, the blocks from rock fall might reach the road.

Table 1. RHRS applied on rock slopes stretches, Westboro and Tunney's Pasture Sectors – Suggested Heights

Geometric Parameters - RHRS				Rating Criteria of RHRS					Geologic Character - RHRS							Rating	
SLOPE	Slope Height (m)	Length (m)	Ditch (m)	Slope Height	Ditch Catchment	AVR	Sight Dist. (m)	R.way Width	Structural Condition 1	Rock Friction 1	Structural Condition 2	Rock Friction 2	Block Size	Water	History	Total RHRS	Normal RHRS
Slope 1	5	25	2.5	25 ft	Moderate	5%	Moderate	20 ft	Favorable	Planar	Occasional	Moderate	1.0	High 1	Many	210	0.22
Slope 2	6	50	2.5	25 ft	Moderate	10%	Moderate	20 ft	Favorable	Planar	Occasional	Moderate	1.0	High 1	Many	216	0.22
Slope 3	7	75	2.5	25 ft	Moderate	15%	Moderate	20 ft	Favorable	Planar	Occasional	Moderate	2.0	High 1	Many	228	0.23
Slope 4	8	75	2.5	50 tf	Limited	15%	Limited	20 ft	Favorable	Planar	Occasional	Moderate	2.0	High 1	Many	276	0.28
Slope 5	9	75	2.5	50 tf	Limited	15%	Limited	20 ft	Favorable	Planar	Occasional	Moderate	2.0	High 1	Many	282	0.29
Slope 6	10	75	2.5	50 tf	Limited	15%	Limited	20 ft	Favorable	Planar	Occasional	Moderate	2.0	High 1	Many	288	0.30
Slope 7	11	75	2.5	50 tf	Limited	15%	Limited	20 ft	Favorable	Planar	Occasional	Moderate	2.0	High 1	Many	294	0.30
Slope 8	12	75	2.5	50 tf	Limited	15%	Limited	20 ft	Favorable	Planar	Occasional	Moderate	2.0	High 1	Many	300	0.31
Westboro	7	150	2.5	25 ft	Moderate	45%	Limited	20 ft	Favorable	Planar	Occasional	Moderate	1.0	High 1	Many	234	0.24
Tunney's	8	250	2.5	50 tf	Limited	73%	Limited	20 ft	Favorable	Planar	Occasional	Moderate	2.0	High 1	Many	282	0.29

In RHRS, the parameter related directly to a major factor for rockfall risks is the slope angle. Once the slopes of Transitway are almost at 90°, this value may not have an influence on the results. Fig. 4 exemplifies a block resulted from rockfall observed in the slopes of the geological formation of Transitway (O’Train stretch). In this image, also debris are found as pieces of evidence of rockfall.

Figure 4. Rockfall at O-Train Carling station

5 EARTHQUAKES AND RISKS IN ROCK SLOPES

Ottawa has been identified as the city with the third highest earthquake risk in Canada (Motazedian et al. 2011). Rock slopes have their stability incredibly challenged during earthquakes and may come to a failure.

The most recent important earthquake in Ottawa area happened in June, 23th of 2010 at 13:41 h (local time) with 5.0 M in Richter scale. Its epicenter was located 55 km of Ottawa (45.904°N; 75.497°W). Aylsworth et al. (2000), considering some geological evidence, suggested that massive earthquakes took place in Ottawa’s St. Lawrence River valleys. These earthquakes, according to the author had the magnitude greater than 7.0 in Richter scale. Figure 5 shows 15 earthquakes with 5 M or greater and one earthquake greater than 6 M. Considering the hazard of 0.002 (Canada Earthquake, 2013) for conventional structures, this work examines the 5 M as one that can potentially induce landslide, and so the hazard is 0.02.

5.1 Vibration induced by the transit of buses

The vehicle-induced vibrations are equivalent to small earthquakes, once the international Modified Mercalli scale compares the vibration in its moderate intensity degree (IV) with heavy vehicle inducing vibrations. And this means an equivalency up to 3.9 M earthquake. This is an important effect and should be considered in any future stability analysis of these slopes. Its relevance may be as greater as

any other issues affecting the long term deterioration of the Transitway rock slopes.

The relevant parameters of distance from the source of impact force, frequency, and intensity might all have considerable influence on the crack generation in the rock mass close to the slope face.

Figure 5. Propagation of vehicle-induced vibrations (from Budetta and Nappi, 2013)

6 THE POSSIBILITY OF ROCKSLIDES

Which level remains over the probability of a rockslide in the Transitway rock slopes? The first set of discontinuities of a limestone is the horizontal one. Once this set is not favorable to form a usual slice of a planar failure, is it possible to neglect its occurrence? May be for static loads.

The limestone of the area, in the same geological formation, the City of Ottawa (2010) found other three sets of discontinuities. The geotechnical parameters of rock slopes can be considered regarding the failure mode chosen for the stability analysis. There are two essential components in a rock slope: i) the matrix of the rock and ii) the discontinuities. For the discontinuities, the dip angle and the strike of the additional joints can define the behavior and so the geomechanical model of the slope.

A slope stability analysis should consider the correct geological and geotechnical parameters of a chosen model, accurate data from field and laboratory test of the discontinuities, the infill of the joints and the same for the matrix of the rock. A reliable assessment of these factors will lead to an evaluation of the current status of the Safety Factor. Ling and Cheng (1997) presented the consecrated slice of Hoek and Bray (1977), and also FHWA (1989), Figure 6. It relies on the derivation of the equations considering the seismic coefficients for the pseudo-static analysis. In this parametric study, a 0.3 horizontal seismic coefficient was deemed to be impossible to happen.

Figure 6. Rock mass plane sliding (Ling and Cheng, 1997)

Kim (2012) summarized the available horizontal seismic coefficient in literature. Since Terzaghi (1950) until Anderson et al. (2008), many works were presented. This range varies from 0.1 to 0.15, and it was the conclusion about this omnipresent parameter in a rock slope stability analysis, and therefore, this work adopted both numbers. Another geological characteristic of the Ottawa's limestone slopes of Transitway is the embedment angle, which varies from 1 to 2° in the City of Ottawa (2010) Report.

This study considered these angles unfavorable to the stability. Fig. 7 exemplifies these considerations. Some parameters were fixed to analyze the behavior of FS with different friction angles at the discontinuities in the case of an earthquake. The cohesion between the discontinuities is considered zero, the angle of the slope is considered 89°, the angle of the embedment is 2° and the unit weight of the rock is 26 kN/m³.

Figure 7. Two typical set of joints in the rock slopes of the geological formation of the area.

The rock slopes between Dominion and Bay View stations can be considered a major stretch of the Transitway which represents this work. There are also rock slopes in O Train between Bay View and Carleton stations. The minimum factor of safety calculated for a static rockslide is greater than 4 with the data used in this work.

Although, the FS found in the pseudo-static analysis to consider the effect of an earthquake were much lower. Figure 8 shows the results of FS for κ_h equal to 0.1 and 0.15 studied with 4 different friction angles between the discontinuities, from 12 to 21°, for H=1.0 m (slice) and Z = z_w = 0.95 m. There is an intense variation of the FS with the friction angle of the discontinuities. An κ_h equal to 0.1 would refer to an earthquake of 6.5 M and the minimum FS found was lower than 0.75 for the minimum friction angle. A stable Factor of Safety for this configuration only happens for friction angle equal to 21°. The model was also used to study a greater slice. Bringing H to 1.50 m (slice) and Z and z_w to 95% of H, the results are the same. Varying the Z together with z_w, the greater is the relation with H, lower is the SF. A smaller Z value means that the crack will happen deeper in the slope, with a great distance from its face. For Z and z_w equal to 90% of H, the result is shown in Figure 9. For the same κ_h equal to 0.1, the minimum FS found was smaller than 1 for the minimum friction angle.

It is relevant to state that changes in the embedment angle of just 1° can change the FS for the same slice in 20% until 5° of embedment for an intermediary friction angle of 18°.

Therefore, this determinist analysis can be analyzed using statistic methods for the variation of the parameter of the model.

Figure 8. Factor of Safety vs friction angle of rock slopes for H =1.0 m (slice) and Z = z_w = 0.95 m.

Figure 9. Factor of Safety vs friction angle of rock slopes for H =1.50 m (slice) and Z = z_w = 1.35 m

6.1 Numerical Analyses of Rock Slope Stability Under Dynamic Loading

To obtain the stress states and kinematics of slopes under dynamic loading, numerical techniques have been widely used in the evaluation of slope stability. The propagation of stress waves in a rock as a three-phase porous medium can be assessed by the following linear momentum balance equation (Khoei and Mohammadnejad, 2011):

$$\nabla \cdot \sigma + \rho \mathbf{b} - n \left[S_g \rho_g \frac{D}{Dt} \left(\frac{\mathbf{W}_g}{n S_g} \right) + S_w \rho_w \frac{D}{Dt} \left(\frac{\mathbf{W}_w}{n S_w} \right) \right] = 0$$

where σ is the total stress, ρ refers to bulk density, \mathbf{b} denotes the body force, second order time-derivative of displacement \mathbf{u} represents the acceleration of the solid phase \mathbf{u} , n is porosity, S_α refers to the degree of saturation with respect to phase α and $\alpha = g$ or w for interstitial gas or water, and \mathbf{W}_α denotes the Darcy velocity of a fluid phase and $\mathbf{W}_\alpha / n S_\alpha$ implies the relative velocity with respect to solid phase. The failure or massive displacement of a slope during

dynamic loading can be induced by both the inertial force and generation of excess pore pressure during vibration. Finite element and finite difference methods have been conventionally adopted to analyze slope response under dynamic loading, and the stability is generally evaluated in terms of slope displacements (e.g. Latha and Garaga, 2010; Khoei and Mohammadnejad, 2011).

These continuum methods are appropriate when the slope consists of weak rock/soil or rock masses where failure is dominated by the deformation of the intact material (Stead et al., 2006). Although these approaches can provide stress states and kinematics as well as accommodate large deformation of slopes, the controlling role of discontinuities in rock mass on slope stability cannot be explicitly considered. However, the mechanisms and intensity of rock mass failure during dynamic loading are found to be highly dependent on the peak velocity caused by incident waves. Thus, kinematics obtained from continuum methods have also been used in the stability analysis of exposed and jointed rock mass in an indirect manner (e.g. Liu et al., 2017).

7 RISK SCENARIOS DUE TO ROCK LANDSLIDES

The hazards of rockfall and rockslide result in different risks for Ottawa Transitway. In Transitway, there are many categories of elements: population (users), equipment, facilities, and properties.

A block due to a rockfall may cause a bus accident with the bus colliding on a block which may reach the road. A landslide may cause facility damage present in its area and adjacent properties. It seems that any volume of a landslide may cause disruption of Transitway for hours, depending on the volume of the rock or soil mass displaced.

In the case of a bus accident, there are possibilities of victims. Between 1990 and 1999, bus occupants represented 4.1% of all fatalities (Transport Canada, 2002) in urban areas related to transport (pedestrian, bus, and other vehicles) in Canada. Bus collisions injuries more than 34,000 per year in the USA and Europe and the fatalities are greater than 475 every year (Kaplan, 2012). In transit bus, 13 passenger and 8 drivers deaths were reported between 1999 and 2005 in the USA. In a detailed study about the location of collisions in Denmark, Kaplan (2012) presented that about 30% of the bus crashes happened in urban areas and 8.7% of them were caused by an object on the road. In the USA, 42.3% of all accidents with transit bus also happened due to collisions in an object on the road (FMCSA, 2009).

7.1 Elements at Risk

This work will consider some elements at risk: the buses, the facilities of the operator, the external facilities and the passenger which are users of the system. An indirect element is, for example, non-users which can be affected as consequence of disruption of the Transitway. This work proposes the evaluation of the risk for the described direct elements which are closely related to the hazards of the rock slope.

7.2 Hazards to the elements

The hazards to the elements have different levels depending on the type of landslide: rockfall or rockslide.

The rockfall hazard will be considered as one event per 2 years that can reach the road and eventually cause a collision. Therefore, H is 0.5. This assumption is not far from reality because the ditch is lower than that one preconized and the presence of blocks due to rockfall in the area is a material evidence.

The rockslide is a major factor due to the frequency of the earthquakes in the area. An earthquake with the magnitude 5 or 6 can cause a rockslide in the Transitway. The hazard of an earthquake can be considered as 0.02.

The chance to happen a bus accident due to a landslide is its hazard multiplied by the frequency of buses showed by the concept AVR of the RHRS (FHWA, 1993). The bus accident due rockfall hazards is between 0.005 and 0.073, depending on the section. For the rockslide, the hazard is between 0.009 and 0.015.

7.3 Vulnerability and Amount

Considering the data of USA, the total bus collisions sums 63,000 events of traffic accidents. These accidents resulted in 14,000 injuries and 325 fatalities. Dividing the events by the victims, the vulnerability can be roughly estimated. For injured people, the vulnerability is 0.22. And 0.005 represents the vulnerability of fatalities for each bus accident in the USA. These also mean that one person may be injured for each 5 bus accident and one death can occur for each 200 bus accident.

Although the medium speed in the public transportation system of the buses is "only" 26,1 km/h, the average speed in a Transitway reaches 80 km/h (Hook et al., 2008) the highest average ever known, where the speed limit of main section is 90 km/h.

One important observation is the speed of the accidents. Only 20% of them happened in speeds of 80 km/h or greater. Applying the rule that 80% of deaths are in these 20% of accident, the vulnerabilities become 0.88 (88%) for injured people and 0.02 (2 %) for deaths.

The vulnerability for victims of these speeds may be underestimated and is probably greater than the average. Several accidents were reported in Transitway. On Feb. 2012 injured 12 people. A bus-train collision in 2013 injured 30 people and 6 deaths were reported.

These data suggest that if an accident in Transitway happens because of an object like a block from rockfall in the road, the possible collision might have led to injuries and casualties.

When it comes to accidents in Transitway, it seems that one in each 2 reported by the media had victims, so the vulnerability is 50%.

The repair of a buss collision may cost 20 to 30% of its value, if the collision is due to damages in the front.

The vulnerability of one bus will be considered as 0.3. The vulnerability of the land and public utilities in the area of the landslide is not estimated in this work. These damages will be estimated as consequences.

7.4 The Amounts

The amounts of this work are limited to operation disruption of the Transitway, buses, facilities, and victims.

The estimated values of these amounts are stated in this item. Disruption in operation will be treated as a consequence. The bus itself, the vehicle has cost for the city the value of \$ 140,000.00. A bus collision will force a minimum repair of the vehicle.

The repair of the facility included the external facility of the city, as sewers, earthwork to recover any loss of mass, and construction to recover the slope. The external works are estimated in \$ 120,000.00. Active economic population, in general, hire life insurance in Canada. It may be greater than the average of \$ 36,000.00 per capita.

An injured person inside a transit bus due to a collision may claim to compensations if its causes could be avoided. Regarding the accidents exemplified before, an injured woman has claimed for CAD\$ 1.4 mi (Willing, 2013). A bus crash in Toronto, where also one woman died had a claim of \$ 4.25 mi launched (CBC News, 2012).

7.5 Direct Consequences

Bonachea et al. (2009) used the concept of direct consequences to evaluate the risks of slopes and suggested to build scenarios from the most optimistic to the worst.

Considering the Transitway's infrastructures, traffic, vicinity with roads and buildings, and finally the speed of the buses, this work proposes consequences regarding the failures of a slope in Transitway as the following scenarios, summarized in Table 2:

A) Level A, the most optimistic scenario – littler disruption of one lane or both lanes due the fall of small rock blocks reported by the operation of the traffic.

B) Level B, small accident as a collision of the bus at low speed due to a small or a medium block which can fall and roll on the road with a disruption less than 6 hours.

C) Level C, a large scale disruption is the main issue of this scenario – a failure of a slope with a sufficient amount of soil and rock which needs more than 6 hours to be removed. The recovery requires construction works. No collision accident and no external facility damaged in this scenario;

D) Level D, a large scale landslide will be the major event – a failure of a slope with a significant amount of soil and rock which needs more than 6 hours to be fixed with no bus accident and extended damages to nearby infrastructures such as roads, public utilities, and buildings;

E) Level E, the most dangerous and pessimist scenario – a significant accident as a collision of the bus at high speed due to a small, big block or landslide which can hit any bus at its maximum speed (90 km/h).

The presence of disruption of service is a primary concern in all scenario because the minimum safety is necessary for Transitway operation. It obligates the transit buses to use the conventional city roads. And this has a high cost for the city and its citizens due to more time spent on the same trip.

Roche (2012) reported that an accident in Transitway in Tunney's Pasture followed by a disruption of 4 hours enforced the buses to use the streets in the way, and so the traffic jam generated went until Kent Street. During 4 hours, a consequence of a 3 km of traffic jams. One road like Richmond/Wellington may accumulate 500 vehicles per hour. The time of a trip may increase 20 minutes per vehicle, coming up with the total time loss of 660 hours. If the occupancy of a car is 1.5 person, the total loss of time could be 990 hours. The value of the job hour is between \$ 10.00

and \$ 100.00. The buses transporting around 80 people each, in 4 hours, with 30 minutes of additional time for each passenger, the number of buses is around 400, and so the total number of passengers starts from 25,000. The same concept of \$ 20.00 for the job hours leads to the total of \$ 500,000.00 due to time loss generated by traffic jams per 4 hours.

Table 2. Hazards and consequences of landslides

Scenario	GeoHazard		Consequence Description			
	Rock Fall	Rock Slide	Disruption in Operation	Bus Accident	Facility Damage	Victims
A	0.5	No	< 6 hours	No	No	No
B	0.5	No	< 6 hours	Yes	No	Yes
C	Y/N	0.02	> 6 hours	No	No	No
D	Y/N	0.02	> 6 hours	No	Yes	No
E	Y/N	0.02	> 6 hours	Yes	Yes	Yes

The cost to repair the facilities included the external utilities of the city, as sewers, earth work to recover any loss of mass and construction to rebuild the slope or its stabilization. The external works are estimated in \$ 120,000.00 for level D and \$ 240,000.00 for level E.

Table 3 summarized the quantities presented and showed the risk value per year. Only one victim was considered to compare the influence of each one.

Table 3. Risk per year according to possible scenarios

Scenario	Consequence Values (after Vulnerability)				RISK per Year (\$)
	Disruption in Operation	Bus Accident	Facility Damage	Victims	
A	125,000.00 (1h)	No	No	No	62,500.00
B	125,000.00 (1h)	42,000.00	No	1,400,000.00 (1)	783,500.00
C	750,000.00 (6h)	No	No	No	15,000.00
D	4,500,000.00 (36h)	No	120,000.00	No	92,400.00
E	4,500,000.00 (36h)	84,000.00	240,000.00	4,250,000.00 (1)	181,480.00

8. CONCLUSIONS

The assessment of the risk of the rock slopes could lead to the following conclusions:

- There were pieces of evidence that the Transitway rock slopes are deteriorating due to coupled effects of weathering and vibrations;
- Earthquakes are a major factor to consider in these rock slope stability which may lead to FS lower than 1;
- Slopes are posing considerable risks because the hazards range of rockfall is between small to intermediary level
- Rockslide induced by an earthquake is a real possibility;
- FS of the slopes and risk status need to be updated with some state-of-the-art tools;
- The application of practical methods, such as RHRS demonstrated its practical view of the problem, even in a low-risk perception scenario.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author acknowledges Capes, the Brazilian Agency of the Brazilian Ministry of Education of personnel development for

financing his studies inside the Ph.D. program at University of Ottawa.

REFERENCES

- Anderson DG, Martin GR, Lam I, Wang JN (2008). *Seismic analysis and design of retaining walls, buried structures, slopes, and embankments*. National Cooperative Highway Research Program, Report 611.
- Aylsworth, J.; Lawrence, D.E.; Guertin, J. 2000. Did two massive earthquakes in the Holocene induce widespread landsliding and near-surface deformation in part of the Ottawa Valley, Canada, *Geology*, v. 28; no. 10; p. 903–906.
- Bonachea, J.; Remondo, J.; Ramo, J.; Teran, J. (2009); Gonzalez-Diez, A.; Cendrero, A. 2009. Landslide Risk Models for Decision Making, *Risk Analysis*, Vol. 29, No. 11: 1629-1643.
- Budetta, P.; Nappi, M., 2013. Comparison between qualitative rockfall risk rating systems for a road affected by high traffic intensity, *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.*, 13, 1643–1653.
- CBC News, 2012. Bus crash victim's family launches \$4.25M lawsuit - Toronto - *CBC News*. www.cbc.ca/news/canada/ottawa/investigators-probe-transitway-bus-crash-1.1151132, accessed 01/Dez/2013.
- Canadian Infrastructure Report, 2012. *Canadian Infrastructure Rep. Card*, Vol.1: 2012, Mun. Roads and Water Systems, <http://canadainfrastructure.ca>, accessed 01 Dez 2013.
- City of Ottawa, 2010. *Geotechnical and Hydrogeological Investigation Ottawa Light Rail Transit (OLRT) Tunnel Ottawa, Ontario*, Golder Associates Ltd., Infrastructure Services & Community Sustainability, City of Ottawa, Ottawa, On, Canada, 399p.
- FHWA. 1989. *Rock slopes : design, excavation, stabilization*, N° FHWA TS-89-045, Spon Press, McLean, VA, USA.
- FHWA. 1993. *Rock Fall Rating System: Participant's Manual*, N° FHWA SA-93-057, Spon Press, McLean, VA, USA.
- FMCSA, 2009. *Bus Operator Types and Driver Factors in Fatal Bus Crashes: Results from the Buses Involved in Fatal Accidents Survey*. 1. Report No. FMCSA-RRA-09-041, Federal Motor Carrier Safety Administration U.S. Dept. of Transportation, Washington, DC, USA
- Hook, W.; Lotshaw, S.; Weinstock, A. 2008. *More Development For Your Transit Dollar - An Analysis of 21 North American Transit Corridors*, Institute for Transportation and Development Policy (ITDP), New York, NY, USA.
- Hook, J.; Lyamin, A.V.; Griffiths, D.V.; Krabbenhoft, K.; Sloan, S.W. 2013. Quantitative risk assessment of landslide by limit analysis and random fields, *Computers and Geotechnics*, No 53: 60–67.
- Kaplan, Prato C.G.S. 2012. Risk factors associated with bus accident severity in the United States: a generalized ordered logic model. *J Safety Res*, 43:171–180.
- Kim, B. (2012). *Seismic hazard analysis and seismic slope stability evaluation using discrete faults in northwestern Pakistan*. University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.
- Khoei, A.R.; Mohammadnejad, T., 2011. Numerical modeling of multiphase fluid flow in deforming porous media : A comparison between two- and three-phase models for seismic analysis of earth and rockfill dams, *Comput. Geotech.*, 38: 142–166.
- Latha, G.M.; Garaga, A. 2010. Seismic stability analysis of a himalayan rock slope, *Rock Mech. Rock Eng.*, 43: 831–843.
- Ling, H.I.; Cheng, A. 1997. Technical Note: Rock Sliding Induced by Seismic Force, *International Journal of Rock Mechanics & Mining Sciences*, Vol. 34, No6:1021-1029.
- Liu, K.; Hao, H.; Li, X. 2017. Numerical analysis of the stability of abandoned cavities in bench blasting, *Int. J. Rock Mech. Min. Sci.*, 92: 30–39.
- Mercier, A. 2008. *Rapid Transit in Ottawa: BRT Today and Tomorrow*, OC Transpo. City of Ottawa. <http://www.uitp-bhls.eu/IMG/pdf/1-2-Alain-Mercier-Ottawa.pdf> accessed 12 Nov 2013.
- OC Transpo, 2012. *OC Transpo annual performance report for 2011*, ACS2012-COS-TRA-0009, Transit Services, City of Ottawa, Ottawa, On, CA, 21p.
- Peckover, F.L. and Kerr, W.G. 1977. Treatment and maintenance of rock slopes on transportation routes, *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 14: 487-507.
- Roche, K. 2012. Bus driver faces charges for Transitway crash, *Ottawa Sun*, <http://ottawasun.com/2012/03/02/bus-driver-faces-bylaw-charges-for-transitway-crash> accessed 4 Nov 2013.
- Stead, D.; Eberhardt, E.; Coggan, J.S. 2006. Developments in the characterization of complex rock slope deformation and failure using numerical modelling techniques, *Eng. Geol.*, 83: 217–235.
- Van Wilkins, V. 2004. Multimodal rapid transit grows in Ottawa. *Mass Transit*, Fort Atkinson, WI, USA, No. 29: 32-38.
- Willing, J. 2012. OC Transpo bus crash prompts another passenger lawsuit. *Ottawa Sun*, 2012, <http://ottawasun.com/2013/11/21/2012-oc-transpo-bus-crash-prompts-another-passenger-lawsuit>, accessed 15 Nov 2013.